

MORPHOLOGICAL AND MOLECULAR-GENETIC IDENTIFICATION OF THE SPECIES OF THE GENUS *SCELIPHRON* KLUG 1801 (HYMENOPTERA: SPHECIDAE)

Kodirov Ixomjon Tojiakhmatovich¹, Boymatov Odiljon Shermatovich²

Namangan State University, Senior Lecturer of the Department of Anatomy and Physiology¹
IxlosbekIsfandiyor@gmail.

Namangan State University, Lecturer of the Department of Anatomy and Physiology²
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15602057>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada *Sceliphron* avlodiga mansub *S. deforme* (F. Smith, 1856), *S. distillatorium* (Illiger, 1807) va *S. madraspatanum* (Illiger, 1807) turlarini aniqlash bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlar haqida ma'lumot berilgan. Ushbu turlar Farg'ona vodiysida birinchi marta qayd etilgan bo'lib, ularning morfologik hamda molekulyar-genetik identifikatsiyasi amalga oshirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Hymenoptera, Sphecidae, *Sceliphron*, tur, mitochondrial DNA, COI.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о проведённом исследовании по идентификации видов *Sceliphron deforme* (F. Smith, 1856), *S. distillatorium* (Illiger, 1807) и *S. madraspatanum* (Illiger, 1807), относящихся к роду *Sceliphron*. Эти виды были впервые зарегистрированы, на территории Ферганской долины, и для их определения были проведены морфологические и молекулярно-генетические исследования.

Ключевые слова: Hymenoptera, Sphecidae, *Sceliphron*, вид, митохондриальный DNA, COI

Abstract: This article provides information about the research on the identification of the species *S. deforme* (F. Smith, 1856), *S. distillatorium* (Illiger, 1807) and *S. madraspatanum* (Illiger, 1807) belonging to the *Sceliphron* genus. These species were recorded for the Fergana Valley for the first time and morphological, as well, molecular genetic identification were performed for these species.

Key words: Hymenoptera, Sphecidae, *Sceliphron*, species, mitochondrial DNA, COI.

Introduction

About 10,145 species of digger bees are known around the world, including 9 species belonging to the family Heterogynaidae, 209 species to Ampulicidae, 808 species to Sphecidae, and 9,121 species to Crabronidae families.

The Apoidea (Hymenoptera: Aculeata) represents a large superfamily consisting of sphecid wasps and bees (or “Anthophila”) [1,7,5]. Apoidea are characterized by a number of morphological character states, especially in larvae [3,8]. Adult sphecid wasps usually prey on other insects or spiders to provide food for offspring. Most sphecids are solitary except for a few species of Crabroninae [3,8]. Most bees are pollinators of angiosperms and provide important ecosystem functions [8]. A number of bee lineages include social insects, a feature shared with related families of ants (Formicidae) and vespid wasps (Vespidae) [4], although the latter are mainly predators.

The genus *Sceliphron* Klug, 1801 belongs to the family Sphecidae, of which 35 species recorded worldwide to date [11,10]. 5 species of representatives of this genus were recorded in Central Asia, in particular, four species, such as *S. curvatum* (F. Smith, 1870), *S. deforme* (F. Smith, 1856), *S. distillatorium* (Illiger, 1807), *S. madraspatanum* (Fabricius, 1781) species were identified in Uzbekistan: [2].

To extract DNA from the specimens, the legs of *S. deforme*, *S. distillatorium* and *S. madraspatanum* belonging to the genus *Sceliphron*, which were stored in a 70% alcohol solution, were placed on dry paper and kept at room temperature for 10-15 minutes until the alcohol evaporated.

For DNA extraction from species of the genus *Sceliphron*, we used 2 ml of 0.5 M Tris HCl, pH 8.5, 10 ml of 2 M KCl solution, 500 µl of 1 M MgCl₂, 2 ml of NP40 and 27 sucrose solution, 200 ml deionized and autoclaved water and 2 ml proteinase K 10mg/ml. Legs of bees belonging to the genus *Sceliphron* placed in Eppendorf tubes were incubated at 65°C for 1-2 hours. After incubation,

solutions of the extraction solution (Lysis buffer+protenase K) were added and kept at 92°C for 10 minutes. Then the extracted DNA samples were stored (-20°C) [6-7].

Polymerase chain reaction from isolated DNA specimens was performed using an automatic programmable amplifier (PR-96E).

Nucleotides of COI fragments of mitochondrial DNA (mDNA) of species of the genus *Sceliphron* were isolated using LEP-F- forward, 5-attcaaccaatcataaagatat-3 and LEP-R-reverse 5-taaactctgtagtgcacaaaa-3 primers widely used in molecular taxonomy [9,12].

The results of the conducted molecular-genetic studies show that the nucleotides with 652 pairs of bases belonging to the COI area of the mRNA of *S. deforme*, *S. destillatorium* and *S. madraspatanum* species belonging to the genus *Sceliphron* were isolated.

In order to determine their specific features, the comparative analysis of the obtained species and the data of NCBI about *S.deforme* (Accession number: OM220040), *S.destillatorium* (Accession number: ON505049) and *S.madraspatanum* (Accession number: MN148443) were conducted (Fig).

According to the results of the conducted molecular genetic research, nucleotides of the obtained *S.deforme* belonging to the genus *Sceliphron* and *S.deforme* from the (NCBI) database (Accession number: OM220040) has 100% similarity, and difference between the 83 nucleotides of the *S. destillatorium* species was determined with 87.3% similarity, and 74 nucleotides difference was found with *S.madraspatanum* species with 88.3% similarity.

Figure . Comparison of the nucleotide sequence of the COI region of mRNA of species belonging to the genus *Sceliphron*.

Nucleotides of the obtained *S. destillatorium* belonging to the genus *Sceliphron* and *S. destillatorium* from the (NCBI) database (Accession number: ON505049) has 100% similarity, and difference between the 70 nucleotides of the *S. madraspatanum* species was determined with 89.3% similarity. It was noted that nucleotides of the obtained *S. madraspatanum* and *S. madraspatanum* from the (NCBI) database (Accession number: MN148443) has 100% similarity.

Nucleotide sequences of species of the genus *Sceliphron* obtained from molecular genetic studies have been deposited in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) and accession numbers have been obtained for the species: *S. deforme* (Accession number: PP598623), *S. destillatorium* (Accession number: PP598621), *S. madraspatanum* (Accession number: PP598620).

According to the results of entomological research conducted in the Ferghana Valley, the species *Sceliphron deforme* (F. Smith, 1856), *Sceliphron destillatorium* (Illiger, 1807) and *Sceliphron madraspatanum* (Illiger, 1807) belonging to the genus *Sceliphron* were identified, and these species were recorded for the first time in the Ferghana Valley.

The molecular genetic identification of these species was carried out and their mRNA was studied by comparing the nucleotide sequence in the COI region. The nucleotide differences between *S. deforme* and *S. distillatorium* species was 12.7%, with *S. madraspatanum* species 11.3%, and 10.7% differences were found between the nucleotides of the *S. distillatorium* species and *S. madraspatanum* species.

REFERENCES

1. Alexander, B.A., 1992. An exploratory analysis of cladistic relationships within the superfamily Apoidea, with special reference to sphecid wasps (Hymenoptera). *J. Hymenoptera Res.* 1, 25–61.
2. Antropov A.V., Yu.V. Astafurova, S.A. Belokobylskij, A.M. Byvaltsev, Yu.N. Danilov, D.A. Dubovikoff, K.I. Fadeev, A.V. Fateryga, N.V. Kurzenko, A.S. Lelej, T.V. Levchenko, V.M. Loktionov, M.V. Mokrousov, P.G. Nemkov, M.Yu. Proshchalykin, P. Rosa, D.A. Sidorov, Yu.N. Sundukov, Z.M. Yusupov, L.A. Zaytseva. Annotated catalog of Hymenoptera insects of Russia. volume I. Sessile bellies (Symphyta) and stinging plants (Apocrita: Aculeata) // *Proceedings of the Zoological Institute RAS Supplement 6, 2017, 475 p.*
3. Bohart, R.M., Menke, A.S., 1976. *Sphecid Wasps of the World.* University of California Press, Berkeley.
4. Danforth, B.N., 2013. Social insects: are ants just wingless bees? *Curr. Biol.* 23, R1011–R1012.
5. Debevec, A.H., Cardinal, S., Danforth, B.N., 2012. Identifying the sister group to the bees: a molecular phylogeny of Aculeata with an emphasis on the superfamily Apoidea. *Zoolog. Scr.* 41, 527–535.
6. Issa M.R.C., Figueiredo V.L.C., Jong D. De, Sakamoto C.H. and. Simões Z.L.P. Rapid method for DNA extraction from the honey bee *Apis mellifera* and the parasitic bee mite *Varroa destructor* using lysis buffer and proteinase K // *Genetics and Molecular Research*, 2013, 12 (4): 4846-4854 p
7. Melo, G.A.R., 1999. Phylogenetic relationships and classification of the major lineages of Apoidea (Hymenoptera), with emphasis on the crabronid wasps. *Animal Sci. Pap. Rep.* 14, 1–55.
8. Michener, C.D., 2007. *The Bees of the World.* Johns Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, USA.
9. Paul D. N. Hebert, Erin H. Penton, John M. Burns, Daniel H. Janzen, and Winnie Hallwachs. Ten species in one: DNA barcoding reveals cryptic species in the neotropical skipper butterfly *Astraptes fulgerator* // *PNAS.*, -2004 vol., 101., 14812–14817 p.
10. Pulawski WJ (2020) *Catalog of Sphecidae sensu lato (= Apoidea excluding Apidae).* California Academy of Sciences, San Francisco. <https://www.calacademy.org/scientists/projects/catalog-of-sphecidae> [accessed July 7, 2020].
11. Schmid-Egger C (2005) *Sceliphron curvatum* (F. Smith 1870) in Europa mit einem Bestimmungsschlüssel für die europäischen und mediterranen *Sceliphron*-Arten (Hymenoptera, Sphecidae). *Bembix* 19 (2005): 7–28.
12. Kadirov T Ilhomjon, Akhmedova Yu Zuhra, Hudoiberdieva O Marifat and Amirov O Oybek. Diagnostics of the two species of *Ammophila* Kirby from Uzbekistan. *Indian Journal of Entomology Online published Ref. No. e23069 DoI. No.: 10.55446/IJE.2023.1213.*